

MS7 Dataset from products and nutritional values for LCA

Lead Beneficiary: UNISG, UCP & DIL

Milestone Description & Contributors

- **Due date:** 31/08/2024
- **Actual submission date:** 31/01/2025
- **Project start date:** September 1st 2021
- **Duration:** 48 months
- **Work package:** WP3
- **Work package leader:** DIL
- **Milestone Title:** Dataset from products and nutritional values for LCA

- **Mean of Verification**

Final data on food and feed products' nutritional analysis will be provided for the RADIANT LCA.

1. Milestone description

The nutritional quality of novel UC products (*1 meat analogue, 1 dairy analogue, 1 bread, 1 small confectionery, 1 pasta and 1 snack, Deliverable 3.6*) are being tested at DIL's and UCP's accredited labs.

2. Mean of Verification

Have you provided the Mean of Verification described in the GA? Yes

Standard compositional analysis near-infrared (NIR) spectroscopy, Soxhlet for lipids, SDS-PAGE for intact proteins using most prominent bands, Dumas for protein content, GC analysis for specific fatty acids, LC analysis for amino acids and sugars, AOAC for fibres are being performed for *DIL and* mineral composition and bioactive components are being performed by UCP using ICP-OES, and bioactive compounds are being characterized using HPLC-DAD, LC-MS, SDSPAGE, FPLC, GC-MS among other techniques ([Deliverable 3.6](#) and Deliverable 3.8). Some selected UC-derived products are being characterised by their bioactive properties. The final datasets of this nutritional analysis will be available in **Deliverable 3.8** (M44) and provided for the RADIANT LCA.